

Performance of Population Control Techniques in Monte Carlo Reactor Criticality Simulations

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ABSTRACT

In Monte Carlo (MC) criticality simulation, fission neutrons accumulated in a generation needs to be properly handled before they can be used as the source particles in the successive generation. There are two well-known methods for handling the so-called fission bank. In the first method, particle weights are normalized to a specified value, say M . In the second method, a population control technique (PCT) is applied so that M particles are sampled from the fission bank. Five distinct PCTs are identified from the literature: simple sampling, splitting-roulette, combing, modified combing, and duplicate-discard. Some of these PCTs have been almost exclusively applied for time-dependent MC simulation. These different methods/techniques have been traditionally seen as mere options to choose from—whether there is a considerable significance on the choices has never been critically investigated. These six methods (weight normalization and 5 PCTs) are implemented to the open-source code OpenMC with streamlined abstraction compatible with the existing parallel fission bank algorithm. Their relative performances are assessed by solving a reactor criticality problem. It is found that techniques that introduce larger uncertainties to particle population produce higher neutron flux tally variances. The significance of the limited parallel scalabilities of some of the techniques are also demonstrated and discussed.

KEYWORDS: Monte Carlo, neutron transport, criticality, population control, parallel algorithm

1. INTRODUCTION

Monte Carlo (MC) method has been an important tool for reactor physicists to perform criticality calculations with minimal approximation. MC criticality simulation has been based on the method of successive generations, which is an MC-adaptation of the power iteration method for solving the k -eigenvalue neutron transport problem. In this method, MC simulation is divided into fission generations. In each generation, the usual MC transport procedure is performed, except that a factor $1/k$ is introduced to the fission neutron yield, and every fission neutron produced is removed from the on-going transport and stored into a particle container known as the fission bank. At the end of each generation, the eigenvalue k is updated and the weights of the neutrons accumulated in the fission bank are normalized to the total number of source particles simulated in the first generation, which is usually specified by MC code users as the number of particles (or histories) per generation; these normalized neutrons in the fission bank are then used as the source particles in the successive generation. The implementation described above not only follows the procedure of the typical power iteration method but also is useful for the MC simulation, because it directs the neutronics system into steady-state configuration and helps maintaining the number of source particles simulated at each generation around the user-specified value. This implementation can be seen as the original procedure of MC criticality simulation and has been implemented in some production MC codes, including MCNP [1] and TRIPOLI-4 [2].

The weight normalization approach described above may suffer from highly-fluctuating number of source particles, particularly if the initial guesses of the eigenvalue k and the “eigenvector” neutron distribution are poorly chosen. While such possible issue has never become a major problem in practice, there is a well-known procedural variation that effectively eliminates it: instead of normalizing weights of the fission bank particles to the user-specified number of particles per generation, say M , we randomly sample M particles from the fission bank. This ensures that exactly M source particles are simulated at each generation. This alternative approach has been implemented in many production MC codes, which include Serpent [3], OpenMC [4], Shift [5], MVP [6], RMC [7], and MCS [8]. Most of the references do not clearly describe how the M particles are actually sampled from the fission bank in their respective MC codes. The simplest way to do it is perhaps to naively draw M samples from the fission bank [6]. A different procedure is used in Serpent [3]: instead of drawing M samples, it randomly duplicates or discards some of the particles in the fission bank to achieve the desired population size. These different approaches (whether to normalize particle weight or not) and sampling procedures have been traditionally seen as mere options to choose from—whether there is a considerable significance on the choices has never been critically investigated.

A recent study by the authors [9] categorizes the naive simple sampling (SS) and duplicate-discard (DD) sampling procedures described above as population control techniques (PCTs). The study defines PCT as a technique that takes an initial population of size N and returns an unbiased final population with size exactly, or close to, a target size M . In a MC criticality simulation, the initial and final populations are respectively the fission bank and the resulting source bank for the successive generation. The study identifies three other PCTs in the literature: particle combing (CO) [10,11], splitting-roulette (SR) [12], and the modified particle combing (COX) [13]. Different to SS and DD, these PCTs have been almost exclusively applied for time-dependent MC simulation. The study shows that the five identified PCTs introduce some uncertainties, with different magnitudes, into the particle population. The uncertainty comes in the form that each individual particle in a fission bank may be sampled/copied several times, or none at all, to the source bank of the successive generation—and the study demonstrates that this additional uncertainty affects the resulting tally variance. Furthermore, it is also observed that parallel implementations of some of the PCTs have limited scalability, which may be an issue for massive parallel computation.

In the previous study [9], the five PCTs are implemented to a Python-based research code, and simple mono-energetic slab problems are used to demonstrate the significance of the different techniques. In this paper, we implement the five PCTs (SS, DD, SR, CO, and COX), as well as the normalization approach, to the open-source production code OpenMC [4] and compare their relative performances by solving a more realistic continuous-energy reactor criticality problem. The following sections are outlined as follows. In Sec. 2, the procedures of the PCTs are described, followed by a brief discussion on their associated theoretical uncertainties. In Sec. 3, we discuss how the distinct techniques are implemented in OpenMC by leveraging the existing, and widely-adapted [4,5,7,8], parallel fission bank algorithm [14]. Section 4 describes the reactor criticality test problem and discusses the results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Sec. 5.

2. THE POPULATION CONTROL TECHNIQUES

Let us consider a MC criticality simulation with M particle histories per generation. The typical fission reaction procedure is assumed, where fission neutrons are emitted with a uniform unit weight. At the end of a generation, N ($\neq M$) neutrons are accumulated in the fission bank. In the normalization approach [1,2], the neutron weights are normalized by reassigning each neutron with the normalized weight M/N , and then the normalized fission bank can be used right away as the source bank for the successive generation. This can be seen as the case without population control, where the successive generation starts with N particles, each with normalized weight M/N . If one wishes to start the successive generation with exactly M particles, each with a unit weight, a population control technique (PCT) is needed.

In Simple Sampling (SS) [6], we randomly draw M particle samples from the fission bank. In Duplicate-Discard (DD) [3], we randomly duplicate (for $N < M$) or discard (for $N > M$) particles from the fission

bank to achieve the desired population size M . One can improve the duplicate mechanism of DD by first duplicating the initial particles $\lfloor M/N \rfloor$ times, and then sampling the remainder $(M \bmod N)$ to achieve the total size M .

Figure 1: Illustration of the combing (CO) and modified combing (COX) techniques.

Figure 1 illustrates how Particle Combing (CO) [10] and Modified Particle Combing (COX) [13] work with $N = 6$ and $M = 4$, where ξ denotes a uniform random number from 0 to 1. In CO, a comb with M uniformly-distanced teeth is offset by $\xi N/M$ and used to comb the N initial particles. The initial particles get copied as many as the number of hits, and the copied particles make the final population. In the example, Particles 1, 3, 4, and 6 are copied once by CO. Different to CO, instead of using uniformly-spaced teeth and sampling the offset of the whole comb, COX allows its teeth to be non-uniformly spaced by offsetting each tooth with a different random number. In the example of COX shown in Fig. 1, Particles 1 and 3 are copied once, while Particle 5 is copied twice.

Sweezy et al. [12] note that there is a possible correlation issue in CO if the initial particles are not randomly ordered. Nevertheless, there has never been any observable effect from such issue in the practical application of the technique [11,9]. COX to some extent remedies this possible correlation issue. However, this remedy comes at the expense of increased uncertainty introduced to the population [9]. This is demonstrated in Fig. 1, where Particles 2 and 5 have an additional possibility to be copied twice by COX, while they can only be copied once or not at all by CO.

Finally, in Splitting-Roulette (SR) [12], we assign the initial particles with a uniform probability of $p = M/N$. We split each particle into $\lfloor p \rfloor + 1$ copies, and then Russian-roulette the last copy with a probability of survival $p - \lfloor p \rfloor$. We note that SR does not exactly produce a final population of size M —nevertheless, the technique is unbiased. The total particle weight sourced in the successive generation is still M , such that all tallies accumulated should be divided by M , not by the actual number of particles sampled by the technique.

2.1. Uncertainty Introduced by the Techniques

To properly measure the uncertainty introduced by the PCTs, one needs to acknowledge that weight normalization is actually applied to the fission bank *before* population control is performed. This means, population control is actually applied to a normalized fission bank, where there are N particles, and each particle i has weight $w_i = M/N$ ($i \in [1, N]$). The resulting final population will be of size M and

have uniform unit weight. The final population is unbiased only if the expectation of the initial particle weight w_i is preserved—that is, if C_i denotes number of copies of initial particle i in the final population: $\mathbf{E}[C_i] = M/N$. All of the five PCTs satisfy this requirement. However, they have some finite uncertainty in C_i (standard deviation $\sigma[C_i] \geq 0$) [9], which are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Relative uncertainty (standard deviation) introduced by different PCTs. The figure is adapted from [9]. N and M denote the fission bank and the targeted source bank sizes, respectively. The shaded yellow area shows possible values of COX.

Figure 2 indicates that the uncertainty introduced is not only dependent on the type of PCT, but also on the ratio N/M . In a MC criticality simulation, we have a fixed value of M (which is the user-specified number of histories per generation). However, the value N can be very different at each generation. Nevertheless, once eigenvalue "convergence" is achieved, after which one would start accumulating tally results, near-steady-state configuration is established, and the ratio N/M oscillates around unity. Around this range, it is found that SR and CO has the minimum uncertainty, closely followed by DD; on the other hand, COX has considerably larger value, while SS has the largest. It is worth mentioning that PCTs introduced their respective uncertainties to the simulated particle population at the end of each generation. We hypothesize that this PCT uncertainty may impact MC tally results, such that the larger $\sigma[C_i]$ of the PCT being used, the larger the resulting tally standard deviations. We note that in the absence of PCT, which is the case for the original normalization approach [1,2], there is no uncertainty introduced ($\sigma[C_i] = 0$) regardless of the ratio N/M .

It should be emphasized that this uncertainty introduced by PCT is not a bias. There is a well-known bias associated with the method of successive generations (which can be mitigated given sufficiently large number of histories per generation) [15]. This bias is introduced when the fission bank is normalized, which is in effect regardless whether population control is applied. PCT neither enhances nor eliminates this bias—it merely introduces additional uncertainty to the already-bias simulation.

3. IMPLEMENTATION IN OPENMC

The five PCTs (SS, DD, SR, CO, and COX), as well as the normalization approach, are implemented to the open-source code OpenMC [4]. C++ abstract class is employed for streamlined implementations. Parallel algorithms of the PCTs provided in [9] are adopted by leveraging the existing parallel fission bank

algorithm [14] to maintain the scalability and reproducibility of the code. This essentially results to a generalized version of the original parallel algorithm, which is illustrated in Fig. 3. The Population Control block shown in Fig. 3 can be any of the five PCTs, which can be set via OpenMC’s Python API attribute `Settings.population_control`.

Figure 3: Illustration (adapted from [14]) of particle bank handling and population control in a parallel criticality simulation.

In the case of the normalization approach, the Population Control block and the setting up of Sample Bank are by-passed; the nearest-neighbor bank-passing algorithm is directly applied to the Fission Bank. Since the size of the Fission Bank is N (not M), the number of work per processor (initially 250) needs to be properly readjusted. Finally, once the bank-passing process is completed, weight normalization is locally performed by each processor to the resulting Source Bank.

It is worth mentioning that population control in OpenMC has been done using SR technique followed by a “fix up” to ensure exactly M particles are sampled. Theoretically, the fix up is unnecessary and introduces bias to the impacted particles in the fission bank. However, the bias may be negligible in practice, especially since M is typically very large. Nevertheless, this SR with bias fix up is not considered in this study—the unbiased SR implementation is used instead.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We consider the simplified 2D model of OPR1000 from [16] (hereafter is referred to as OPR2D). We run the criticality problem of the OPR2D model* with 10^7 particle histories in 200 passive and 300 active generations, using the five different PCTs and the normalization technique. Besides the criticality k , pincell-wise thermal ($E \in [0, 0.625 \text{ eV}]$) and fast ($E \in [0.625 \text{ eV}, 2 \text{ MeV}]$) neutron fluxes are tallied as well. The simulations are run in LLNL’s compute platform Quartz (Intel Xeon E5-2695 v4) with 36 MPI processes and 72 OpenMP threads/process. Finally, the simulation of each of the six cases (5 PCTs and the normalization technique) is repeated 50 times with different random number seeds.

Given the accurate simulations, similar tally mean values (within uncertainties) are obtained using the six techniques. From one of the simulation results, it is found that $k = 1.074712 \pm 1.5 \text{ pcm}$, which is associated

*The OpenMC model for the problem is obtained from <https://github.com/mit-crpg/benchmarks>.

with pincell flux distributions shown in Fig. 4. However, to assess the relative performances of the different techniques, we are interested in comparing the magnitude of the standard deviations, as well as the runtimes of the parallel simulations.

Figure 4: A neutron flux MC solution of the OPR2D problem. The median of the associated relative standard deviation (not shown in here) is about 0.31%.

Standard deviations of the pincell flux distribution, resulted from the 6×50 simulations, are compared in jittered box plots shown in Fig. 5. We note that “None” represents the normalization technique (the case without population control). Standard deviations of the criticality are also compared in the same manner (not shown here)—however, there is no meaningful difference observed between the values obtained from the six different techniques.

Figure 5: Average standard deviations of pincell-wise neutron fluxes calculated using different population control techniques. The unit is relative difference to the median value of the normalization technique, “None”.

Figure 5 compares the average standard deviations of the pincell neutron flux distributions. The values are shown in relative difference to the median value of the normalization technique (note that the value is zero at None’s median). We found that the normalization technique, DD, SR, and CO similarly produce the lowest average standard deviations, while COX and SS respectively has slightly and considerably higher

values. This is in agreement with the theoretical uncertainties that they introduce to the population (cf. Section 2.1 and Fig. 2); this confirms our earlier hypothesis that population control uncertainty introduced to a simulation may affect the resulting tally variance. Furthermore, the effect of the population control uncertainty is found to be stronger in the fast flux compared to the thermal flux. The average standard deviations of fast neutron flux calculated using SS is about 4% higher than those of DD, SR, CO, and the normalization technique; while COX is only slightly ($< 1\%$) higher. The difference seems small, but one should note that it is in the scale of fuel pincell. Moreover, similar relative trend is observed in simulations with different accuracy—particularly for those with lower number of histories per generation, making the population control uncertainty effect more pronounced in absolute value.

Figure 6: Relative difference of the fast flux standard deviation of SS and COX to the normalization technique.

Figure 6 maps the relative difference of the fast flux standard deviations of SS and COX to that of the normalization technique. The compared standard deviations are those that result to their respective median values shown in Fig. 5(b). In other words, Fig. 6 tries to demonstrate where the higher standard deviation of SS (and COX) takes place in the reactor model. The mainly-reddish circle area in Fig. 6(a) indicates that most of the 4% higher average standard deviation of SS (cf. Figure 5(b)) is concentrated right in the core of the reactor. Such a situation is not as observable in the case of COX (cf. Figure 6(b)), whose average standard deviation is just slightly larger ($< 1\%$) than the normalization technique.

Figure 7: Runtime spent from using different techniques in the parallel simulations.

Figure 7(a) shows runtime spent in fission bank handling and population control, which are performed in parallel by the 36 MPI processes used in the simulations. It is found that the normalization technique spent the lowest time as it does not need to perform any population control; nevertheless, it still needs to normalize each particle's weight and perform nearest-neighbor MPI communication, which explains the comparable runtime to some of the other techniques. The particle sampling procedures of SR, CO, and COX (cf. Section 2) are embarrassingly parallel, which allows the techniques to take full advantage of the multiple processors. On the other hand, it is found that SS takes the largest time to perform. This is due to the significant serial sampling procedure of the technique; even though particles are handled locally, each processor needs to draw the whole N samplings to ensure reproducibility. Similar to SS, DD also suffers from a serial sampling procedure, but it is not as significant as SS; in fact, since DD only needs to draw sample as many as $|N - M|$, which is expected to be close to zero upon eigenvalue convergence (especially with high number of particle histories), the runtime of DD is almost the same like those of SR, CO, and COX.

Figure 7(b) shows that the fission bank handling and population control take a considerably large portion of the total runtime (about 27 % for SS, and 14 % for the others). Ideally, one would like to have this portion to be close to zero, so that almost all of the runtime is efficiently spent in the actual parallel transport, and any difference in runtime spent for fission bank handling is negligible. However, in practice, such highly-efficient use of processors may not be achieved most of the times, particularly if getting solutions in a timely manner is more important than efficiently utilizing the available machines. Figure 7 shows that, if a non-optimal use of processors happen to occur, choosing optimal population control techniques matters.

5. CONCLUSION

Five distinct population control techniques (PCTs) identified from the literature are reviewed: simple sampling (SS), splitting-roulette (SR), combing (CO), modified combing (COX), and duplicate-discard (DD). Their application in the method of successive generations for MC criticality simulation is discussed, particularly on how they contrast to the weight normalization technique. Theoretical uncertainty that the PCTs introduce to particle population is also discussed, and is later confirmed that it affects the resulting tally variance. The six different techniques are implemented to the open-source code OpenMC with streamlined abstraction compatible with the existing parallel fission bank algorithm. Their relative performances—based on runtime and neutron flux tally standard deviation—are assessed by solving criticality problem of a simplified 2D model of OPR1000.

Since the weight normalization technique does not perform any population control, it does not introduce any additional uncertainty and runs the fastest compared to the other techniques. This makes it of most ideal techniques to use in MC criticality calculation. However, if one is concerned with its possible issue of highly-fluctuating number of particles, the use of PCT may be preferable. Some PCTs—i.e., SR and CO—are as performant as the normalization technique: they introduce minimum uncertainty and their sampling procedures are embarrassingly parallel. The use of naive, non-optimal PCT like SS should be avoided, as it introduces significantly larger uncertainty and has the most limited parallel scalability. Finally, it is worth mentioning that the parallel PCT algorithm illustrated in Fig. 3 can be generally applied to other MC eigenvalue simulations, such as c - [17] and α -eigenvalues [18], and also to time-dependent MC simulations [9].

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